

Utilization of Public Space in Market Area Wamanggu Case Study Merauke

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ABSTRACT: An urban area grows along with the development of community demands as actors in activities. This means that physically and functionally, the intensity and quality of city activities are always changing. The function of the area as a city-scale service center requires the area to have a high activity intensity. The stronger economic activity in a part of the city tends to change the shape of the existing city. This is because as actors in economic activities, people tend to choose strategic areas. The change in the function of public space into a trading area is due to factors supporting the existence of the location. In the relationship between users in their respective public spaces, they give different responses depending on several things. For this reason, it is necessary to study what aspects affect user behavior in public open spaces. To see various aspects of human behavior, it is necessary to study what attributes affect the environment. Likewise with Merauke Wamanggu Market where its location is in an area that is quite ideal for a trading area located in the center of Merauke City with the surrounding environmental conditions being a trading area. This research was conducted in order to obtain environmental attributes through behavioral phenomena in the Merauke Wamanggu Market Area. With this writing, it is expected to be able to present descriptive data and pictures/graphics/images about the phenomenon of environmental behavior & attributes in the Merauke Wamanggu Market Area in Merauke Regency.

KEYWORDS: Utilization, Public Space Functions, User Behavior

A. INTRODUCTION

The development of an urban area grows along with the development of community demands as actors in activities. This means that physically and functionally, the intensity and quality of city activities are always changing. The function of the area as a city-scale service center requires the area to have a high activity intensity. The stronger economic activity in a part of the city tends to change the shape of the existing city [1]. This is because as actors in economic activities, people tend to choose strategic areas. The change in the function of public space into a trading area is due to factors supporting the existence of the location. In the relationship between users in their respective public spaces, they give different responses depending on several things. For this reason, it is necessary to study what aspects affect user behavior in public open spaces [2]. To see various aspects of human behavior, it is necessary to study what attributes affect the environment. In this research, the main theory from Windley & Scheidt is used. According to Windley & Scheidt in Weisman [3]. Likewise with Merauke Wamanggu Market where its location is in an area that is quite ideal for a trading area located in the center of Merauke City with the surrounding environmental conditions being a trading area. Under these circumstances the market location is a potential area for trading activities that add to the attractiveness for traders to peddle their wares. Even some of the roads around the road are used for selling areas, especially on Paulus Nafi Street, Gor Street and also in the parking area at Wamanggu Market. The Paul Nafi road is the main access to enter the Wamanggu Market,

while the Gor road is the exit from the Wamanggu Market. The existence of the Wamanggu Market is thought to be the trigger for the growth of trading activities followed by changes in the function of public spaces along Paul Nafi Street and Gor Street as well as in the parking area in the Wamanggu Market. In this case, it is necessary to examine the possibility of these changes being influenced by the development of trading facilities (Wamanggu Market) which became the center of trade in Merauke Regency. The users of the public space which in the Environmental and Behavioral Architecture indicate a territorial conflict in the use of space. Based on the background and the problems faced, from the background described above, the formulation of the problem is: What environmental attributes were found in the observation of Architecture and Behavior in the Wamanggu Merauke Market Area, while the purpose of this study was to obtain environmental attributes through the phenomenon of behavior that exists in the Merauke Wamanggu Market Area. With this writing, it is expected to be able to present descriptive data and pictures/graphics/images about the phenomenon of environmental behavior & attributes in the Merauke Wamanggu Market Area in Merauke Regency.

B. MATERIAL AND METHOD

B.1 Time and Location of Research

This research was conducted in June 2021 in the Merauke Wamanggu Market Area with the research location being on Jalan Paul Nafi, Jalan Gor and the Wamanggu Market Parking area Merauke.

Fig. 1. Research Site Map

Fig. 2. Research Area Map

- Sources of Data

The data collected in this study used an exploratory approach to find out the space of interest and the background for choosing the space and what activities were carried out in that space [4]. The data collection carried out in this study was obtained by: 1) Observations used in architectural studies, namely Behavioral Mapping with behavioral mapping using Place-Centered Mapping and Person-Centered Mapping, 2) documentation techniques, 3) interviews.

- Place-Centered Mapping

In this study, the Place Centered Mapping method was used to see how humans organize themselves in a particular location [5] [6] This survey technique aims to find out how humans or a group of humans utilize, use or accommodate their behavior in a certain time and place situation.

- Person-Centered Mapping

This behavioral survey technique emphasizes the movement of people over a certain period of time. Thus this technique will relate not only to one place or location but to several places or locations. This technique also only deals with someone who is specifically observed. The aim is to obtain a mapping of the use of public space in the Wamanggu Merauke Market Area for users and to describe user behavior patterns and activities that occur.

- Research Design

This research method is rationalistic qualitative, namely research procedures that produce descriptive data in the form of written and spoken words from people and observed behavior. The approach is directed at the background and the

individual as a whole/holistic [7] [8].

- Population and Sample

Sampling was carried out on informants who carried out activities in public spaces in the Merauke Wamanggu Market area as the research location. Sampling was done by purposive, the sample was selected with certain criteria, based on certain theories, in accordance with the research objectives.

- Data Collection

There are two types of variables used in this study, namely the influencing variable, which is called the independent variable and the affected variable, namely the dependent variable.

- Data Analysis Method

The data analysis method used there are 3 flows that occur simultaneously [9] : 1) data reduction, 2) data presentation, 3) verification.

C. RESULTS

In research on Community Behavior Patterns on the Utilization of Public Open Spaces in the Merauke Wamanggu Market area, the data collection technique by means of Behavior Mapping consists of 3 (three) locations, namely: 1) Jalan. Paulus Nafi, 2, Jalan Gor, 3) Market Parking Area using Place-centered Mapping and Person-centered Mapping, namely to generate behavioral attributes or phenomena that occur at the research location by taking samples of visitors to every public open space based on the type of facilities provided. Use. The time of the study was carried out in the morning at 06.00-08.00 wit and in the afternoon at 15.00-17.00 wit. The results of Behavior

Mapping observations at the research location can be seen in the image below.

Fig. 3. a-b. Observation Data Behavior Mapping Research Area

Based on the results of Observations (Behaviour Mapping) at the research location there are several groups of traders who are

reviewed based on the facilities used, as for the facilities used, namely:

Table. 1. Observation results (Behaviour Mapping)

Street Paulus Nafi	Street Gor	Area Market Parking
Traders using vehicles (cars)	Lesehan merchant	Lesehan merchant
Merchants using carts	Merchants use tables and tents	Lesehan traders use tents
Lesehan merchant	-	Traders using vehicles (motorcycles)
Lesehan traders use tents	-	Merchants using arco

• Place Center Mapping

The pattern of dominant behavior/tendency of traders in the Merauke Wamanggu Market Area can be seen in the picture below, namely traders are more likely to carry out activities or use public spaces located in the Wamanggu Merauke Market Area, namely on Paulus Nafi Street, traders tend to use the shoulder of the road, and the storefront for To sell, on Streat Gor, traders use the shoulder of the road to peddle the goods they sell and in the parking area of the market, traders use part of the parking area to hold their merchandise. Based on the results of observations and interviews with traders, information was obtained about the reasons why traders chose the location of public spaces to sell, namely:

1. Traders who use vehicles (cars) that they do not have stalls or kiosks at Merauke Wamanggu Market and are close to the center of the crowd and easy to see by visitors who are just passing by or visitors who enter the market so that they can easily offer the goods being sold, while when the buying and selling activities have

been completed the trader will leave the selling location, the location used for selling is not fixed in the same place.

2. Lesehan traders / using tents and arco are traders who have stalls in the market but the position of the booths is less strategic and far from the main circulation area so that the area of the booth they own tends to be quiet. traders choose the location to sell by utilizing public space both on the shoulder of the Paul Nafi road and in the market parking area which is considered close to the crowd and the goods being traded can be easily seen by visitors, this only occurs in the morning at 06.00-08.00 and 15.00 -17.00 pm..
3. traders using tables are traders who have stalls in the market but the position of the stalls is less strategic and far from the main circulation area so that the area of the stalls they have tends to be quiet, so traders choose the location to sell by utilizing public space both on the shoulder of Jalan Gor which is considered close to the

“Utilization of Public Space in Market Area Wamanggu Case Study Merauke”

crowd and goods that are traded can be easily seen by visitors. while the table used is placed on the back side of the selling location and will be used the next day, this only happens in the morning at 06.00-08.00 and 15.00-17.00 wit.

- Traders who use motorbikes are traveling merchants who come to the market to shop for goods to be sold, when carrying out their activities traders tend to park their vehicles in the market parking area, the existence of these traders makes many hawkers offer their wares,

thus making room for movement in the market. the parking area is getting narrower. So there was a seizure of the existing parking area and some visitors parked their vehicles on the shoulder of Paulus Nafi road and in front of the shop on Jalan Gor and some visitors parked their vehicles in the area designated for the loading and unloading area in the parking area of the Wamanggu market, Merauke, this only happened in the morning day 06.00-08.00 WIT.

Fig. 4. a,b,c. Place-Centered Mapping at the Research Site

• Person Centere Mapping

This analysis is carried out using the Behavioral Mapping method, namely Person Centered Mapping, namely by mapping activities that focus on one person within a certain period of time.

This activity mapping is a visualization of the form of activity, activity actors, activity time and location of activities that occur in the public space of the Wamanggu market area of Merauke.

Fig. 4. a,b,c. Person-Centered Mapping on Research Sites

Based on the results of observing the pattern of traders' activity on Jalan Paulus Nafi, Jalan Gor and in the market parking area, it was found that the most activity was carried out in the morning at 06.00 and in the afternoon at 15.00-17.00 wit, traders used more public spaces at that time. quite crowded with visitors.

- Lesehan traders: take goods in the market- lay out sacks/tarpaulins- take out merchandise- arrange goods- sit at the back of the selling area- sit talking with other traders- see and offer merchandise to visitors- stand to serve buyers- haggle for goods -pick up and pack orders-hand over goods-

take and give change-arrange items-sit back in the same place

- b. Lesehan Traders Using Tents: taking goods in the market - setting up tents - laying out sacks / tarpaulins - removing merchandise - arranging goods - sitting at the back of the selling area - sitting talking with other traders - seeing and offering merchandise to visitors - standing and serving buyers-bargain goods-pick up and pack orders-deliver goods-pick up and give change-arrange goods-sit back in the same place
- c. Merchants Using Arco: picking up goods in the market - choosing a place to sell - sitting at the back of the selling area - sitting talking to other traders - viewing and offering merchandise to visitors - standing up to serve buyers - bargaining for goods - taking and wrapping orders - handing over goods-take and give change of money-arrange items-sit back in the same place
- d. Merchants by car: come - choose a place to sell - arrange goods - put up a tent - sit next to a car - sit and talk with other traders - see and offer merchandise to visitors - stand to serve buyers - bargain for goods - take and pack orders - handing over - taking and giving change - arranging things - sitting back in the same place
- e. Merchants by motorbike: come-choose a parking space-shop for goods--arrange items in boxes on the motorbike-leave the parking area
- f. Traders Using the Table: come-pick up and prepare the table-set up the goods-set up the tent-sit behind the counter-sit talking to other traders-view and offer merchandise to visitors-stand to serve buyers-bargain goods-take and wrap orders -handing over - taking and giving change - arranging things - sitting back in the same place
- g. Merchants use carts: come-choose their selling locations-set up tables and chairs-set up tents-sit behind carts-stand to serve buyers-prepare ordered goods-deliver and pack orders-hand over goods-take and give change of money-clean equipment -arrange the equipment-sit back in the same place

D. DISCUSSION

The behavior of traders in choosing a trading location in public spaces in the Wamanggu market area, Merauke in the morning at 06.00-08.00 and in the afternoon at 15.00-17.00 wit according to environmental conditions and activities that occur. Behavior occurs through a process that begins with a stimulus to something, perception, understanding, then the motivation from various backgrounds it has. These conditions are poured in the form of behavior in the environment. Attributes that emerge from this research, namely the tendency of activities carried out by traders starting from coming, carrying out selling activities in public spaces in the Wamanggu market area, Merauke are as follows:

- Accessibility (accessibility)

According to Weisman [10] [11] accessibility is the ease of movement in using space related to circulation/roads and visuals.

In this study, accessibility is translated as proximity to the center of the crowd, traders need proximity to the center of the crowd as a potential to bring in buyers. The results of research on the accessibility attribute show that proximity to the crowd is one of the main factors, even more influential than the comfort attribute. Traders continue to occupy an inconvenient location (without shade, heat, dust, etc.) because their main attribute according to them is accessibility close to the center of the crowd as well as room for movement in using a wider space.

- Crowdedness

Crowd is a situation where a person or group of people is no longer able to maintain their personal space [12]. Some traders also ignore the crowding factor in choosing a location to sell because it allows the accessibility attributes to the center of the crowd to be fulfilled. The behavior of traders who hold or sell using public spaces (Market parking areas) makes the circulation space narrow, this can be seen from the vehicles parked on the shoulders of Paul Nafi and in the loading and unloading area of goods and also the behavior of visitors through the parking area must be under pressure between humans and vehicles (motorcycle) entering or leaving the parking area.

- Visibility

Visibility is the ability of an environment to give an effect so that it can easily see (visually) the desired object at a certain distance [13] [14]. Based on the results of the study, that traders have visibility attributes, where the ease of seeing the arrival of visitors is one of the needs to offer their merchandise to prospective buyers who mostly pass by on Paul Nafi Street, Gor Street and in the market parking area. Based on observations, the tendency of traders to have an orientation towards the circulation path/road with the reason that they do not need a deklit with writing as a visitor's tool to identify the type of their merchandise.

- Activities

Activity is the intensity of behavior that continuously takes place in an environment. In informal groups, different patterns of behavior can emerge as a result of group interaction over time [13] [15]. Based on the results of the study, there are differences in the tendency of traders' activities that occur due to different types of facilities used. Based on place centered mapping, there are differences in the behavior of traders based on the trading facilities used, namely traders selling on a lesehan, using arco most of them are in the market parking area because the target traders are visitors who enter the market, while traders who use cars are mostly on Paulus Nafi Street. because the activity space is more adequate for the trading facilities used, traders who use tables are more dominant on Jalan Gor because the target traders ar[e market visitors and road users. Traders who use carts are found in the parking area and on Paulus Nafi Street with the target of traders being traders who sell in the market all day and shop employees on Paul Nafi Street.

E. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results and discussion and research objectives, it can be concluded that:

1. The behavior or attributes of the community in utilizing public open spaces include: Wamanggu Market namely Legibility (Legibility), Accessibility, Convenience, Territory (Territory), and Privacy.
2. The dominant environmental attributes of people's behavior in public open spaces include: The dominant attributes of Wamanggu market are:
 - a) Legibility can be seen in the behavioral patterns that appear in wamanggu market, which is illustrated in chapter IV, namely the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd behavior patterns. Visitors usually perceive the environment first and then determine where to place activities such as gazebos, park plazas, concrete or seawall seats.
 - b) Privacy is also seen dominant in chapter IV, namely the behavior patterns of the 1st and 5th visitors at Wamanggu Market, namely the behavior pattern of visitors starting from the selection of seats, then visitors usually come alone, in pairs, or with their families by keeping their distance from other visitors so that privacy from visitors stay awake.
 - c) Convenience is seen in chapter iv of the 1st, 5th, and 6th behavioral patterns, visitors prefer to sit in the gazebo so that activities are not always observed and get a high level of comfort, visitors also want their personal space to be maintained

REFERENCES

1. Berg, Magdalena van den, Wanda Wendel-Vos, Mireille van Poppel, Han Kemper, Willem van Mechelen, and Jolanda Maas. 2015. 'Health Benefits of Green Spaces in the Living Environment: A Systematic Review of Epidemiological Studies'. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* 14 (4): 806–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2015.07.008>.
2. Carrs, Stephen, Mark Francis, Leanne G. Rivlin, and Andrew M. Stone. 1992. *Public Space*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
3. Ching, Francis D. K. 2007. *Architecture: Form, Space, and Order*. 3rd ed. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
4. Wikantiyoso, Respati, Aditya Galih Sulaksono, and Tonny Suhartono. 2021. 'Detection of Potential Green Open Space Area Using Landsat 8 Satellite Imagery'. *ARTEKS: Jurnal Teknik Arsitektur* 6 (1): 149–54. <https://doi.org/10.30822/arteks.v6i1.730>.
5. Liem, Yoseph, and Reginaldo Chistophori Lake. 2018. 'Pemaknaan Ruang Terbuka Publik Taman Nostalgia Kota Kupang'. *ARTEKS: Jurnal Teknik Arsitektur* 2 (2): 149–58. <https://doi.org/10.30822/arteks.v2i1.48>.
6. Karuppannan, S., & Sivam, A. (2013). Comparative analysis of utilisation of open space at neighbourhood level in three Asian cities: Singapore, Delhi and Kuala Lumpur. *URBAN DESIGN International*, 18(2), 145–164. <https://doi.org/10.1057/udi.2012.34>.
7. Barbarossa, L. (2020). The Post Pandemic City: Challenges and Opportunities for a Non-Motorized Urban Environment. An Overview of Italian Cases. *Sustainability*, 12(17), 7172.
8. Honey-Roses, J., Anguelovski, I., Bohigas, J., Chireh, V., Daher, C., Konijnendijk, C., & others. (2020). The Impact of COVID-19 on Public Space: A Review of the Emerging Questions [Internet]. *Open Science Framework*; 2020 Apr [cited 2020 May 22]. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/xf7xa>
9. Moser, B., Malzieu, T., & Petkova, P. (2020). *Tactical Urbanism: Reimagining Our Cities post-Covid-19*. Fosterandpartners.Com. <https://www.fosterandpartners.com/plus/tactical-urbanism>
10. Hasibuan, Friska, and Samsu Hendra Siwi. 2019. 'Implementasi Architecture for All Pada Pemanfaatan Ruang Terbuka Hijau Sebagai Ruang Tunggu Di Kantor Pemerintahan'. *Jurnal Bakti Masyarakat Indonesia* 2 (1): 135–44. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jbmi.v2i1.4338>.
11. Aditantri, Rahmatyas, and Rona Fika Jamila. 2019. 'Program Perbaikan Kampung Di Kampung Deret Petogogan, Jakarta Selatan'. *Urban Planning and Property Development Review* 2(1):33–44. <http://journal.podomorouniversity.ac.id/index.php/UPPDR/article/view/104/88>
12. Effendi, Dewinita, Judy O. Waani, and Amanda Sembel. 2017. 'Pola Perilaku Masyarakat Terhadap Pemanfaatan Ruang Terbuka Publik Di Pusat Kota Ternate'. *SPASIAL: Jurnal Perencanaan Wilayah Dan Kota* 4 (1): 185–97. <https://ejournal.unsrat.ac.id/index.php/spasial/article/view/15729/15242>.
13. Pratiwi, Yulia. 2016. 'Transformasi Fungsi Ruang Terbuka Publik Di Perkotaan. Studi Kasus: Taman Pedestrian Kecamatan Tenggaraong, Kabupaten Kutai Kartanegara, Kalimantan Timur'. *NALARs* 15 (1): 63 <https://doi.org/10.24853/nalars.15.1.63-72>.
14. Marsujitullah dan Muhammad Arfah Asis "Integrasi Peta Digital pada Sistem Informasi Lahan Pertanian Kabupaten Merauke, Indonesia" *Jurnal Buletin Sistem Informasi dan Teknologi Islam*, 2022.
15. Marsujitullah, dkk " Geographical Information System (GIS) in Mapping Conservation Areas of Indigenous Peoples in Wasur National Park RI – PNG", *Jurnal Review Of International Geographical Education*, 2021